

Impact of Employees' Behavior on Sales and Marketing: A Case of Sungro PVT LTD

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Abstract:- This case were related to the agriculture company and how Mr Nafees started the company by making teams for sales, marketing, and other departments. The company's most essential and highlighted department is sales and marketing, which generates sales and produces revenue. They trained their sales team, set their sales call, introduced a franchise system, and selected products. Sungro started on January 5, 2012, with 45 people in the sales and marketing team who are on vehicles. In 2013, they revised the strategy of targeting the customer to increase their sales with the help of the sales and marketing departments. They focus on improving the sales and marketing departments through training from some popular Pakistani trainers to set up their sales calls and cover up their weak points. In 2014, they had an agreement with a Japanese company to give them a monopoly product, which they launched to capture the market with the help of the Japanese company, which boosted the sales teams. They spend more on advertising their product and company through all advertising channels. The visit by that Japanese company was a powerful strategy they used to gain the trust of their customers.

Keywords:- Sales, Marketing, Entrepreneur, Management, Skills, Sales and Marketing.

I. SUNGRO PRIVATE LIMITED

In 2015, the target was 2.5 million. Nafees Ahmad fully meet the target; increase the number of managers to monitor the workload appropriately. The OAT president came to Pakistan for a meeting in a hotel in Lahore with 1,000 farmers. That fantastic experience inspired their team to increase sales and re-engage former confident customers who no longer consider them. OATS' president was pleased to see the company clients' positive response and feedback on their ON CALL product. The company's owners successfully obtained new products from OATS's president and permission to produce local ON-CALL granules. The price was low, and sales were high. The company's total sales have now reached \$2.5 billion.

The day was Tuesday, and the date was August 2, 2011. Mr Nafees was sitting in his office when suddenly the door of his room knocked, and three people entered his office; two of them were his old university fellows, but the third was a stranger to him. Who is he? What is the purpose of these men

having to visit my office? Mr Nafees was thinking about all the aspects in a couple of seconds. Then, his friend introduced the third person, whose name was Shafique Pitafi. Now, Mr Shafique tells him the purpose of his visit to Mr Nafees' office and that he wants to start a new business and hire him as the GM of the company. Mr Nafees agrees with him but needs some time to make practical decisions about how to start this journey, where to start this company and the feasibility of running the company. It takes about four months to finalize all the decisions. The primary and most crucial part of decision-making is team building, from where and how to make an effective team to minimize all the risk factors.

On January 5, 2012, the hiring process started to run the company. The sales team initially had only 45 people on four wheels. Then Nafees Ahmad set up a franchise system in their company for this, and Nafees Ahmad have to hire a one-franchise manager to control it and set up a meeting with the dealers to work with them. After that, Nafees Ahmad make a sales and marketing team to run their operation correctly. Beyond all these, Nafees Ahmad must remove many other problems before adequately introducing themselves to the market. The first thing is to decide on the franchise selection—what dealer Sungro PVT LTD have to work with; another decision is product selection—what kind of products Sungro PVT LTD have to launch at the time of the company's launch and what strategy Nafees Ahmad have to adopt or plan to use to sell their product in the market. Team development is an essential point, and how do you train them? How do sales team approach farmers? What sales call do sales person put in front of them to attract them toward their products? Lastly, Sungro have to plan the rules and regulations for their company. Now the Department of the company on which the whole company depends is the marketing department. The marketing department uses above-the-line (ATL) and below-the-line (BTL) marketing strategies. In ATL, marketing mass media channel were being to target a broader range of customers in a shorter period. On the other hand, in BTL marketing, the company uses this strategy when Sungro target a specific group of customers for their product and then advertise on radio, television, print media, etc. Marketing team create marketing materials for franchises to introduce them to new markets. Who are we? Then Nafees Ahmad set up the sales call pitch for their sales and marketing teams to interact with customers and introduce themselves. All the central points are written down in the literature, like the rules and regulations followed by the franchise. Why does any dealer become a franchise?

➤ *Issues were addressed through the training process of the sales team*

All the hiring processes were centralized. After hiring all the sales staff, Sungro have to train them properly. Determine their sales pitch and how sales person will interact with the customer and dealer to reach an agreement on the sale and purchase of their product. Then MR Nafees had to finalize the modalities of the franchise; that is what our outlook looks like, and the central and final thing is to decide the name of the franchise that were selected as, Tahafuz. All their franchises were name as Tahafuz. All the products sold in their franchises were launch with a brand name and proper brand packaging. Then Nafees Ahmad have to set the target for their first launch year, which is \$600 million, and decide what activities sales and marketing have to do to advertise their company in the market and enhance sales. The collection of cash was centralize online system. In the initial phase, products delivered from various warehouses of the company. Until June and July, Nafees Ahmad started facing financial issues, but most of their investment revolved around the market and saw growth in their sales revenue. At that time, Nafees Ahmad sought marketing support to guide people through advertising and conducted seminars and marketing activities. Nafees Ahmad target the focus customer (the farmer) and work on it. Nafees Ahmad begin by emphasizing their core customer and repeatedly emphasizing brands in every gathering to boost sales. The strategy increases customer follow-through, and Nafees Ahmad expect to reach 350 million by August. Sungro PVT LTD closed their first year on 480 million of their target, which Nafees Ahmad set to start at 600 million. That was an impressive achievement. The strategy for 2013 was similar to that of 2012, but the target was one billion rupees. To meet the target, Nafees Ahmad increased their marketing and sales team from 45 to 65 four-wheeled sales people. Nafees Ahmad now introduced their market-loving product through more effective advertising that targets specific customers. Sngro improve their ATL and BTL advertising, their literature printing, and mention their bold customers to motivate others. Nafees Ahmad increase the promotion of their product, and the company for this large gathering is suitable for them. In a short time, Nafees Ahmad can approach many customers with the help of their bold and potential products. However, much of the same product has already been available.

Now customers and franchisees demand a unique product that is very difficult to establish a mark for and a monopoly in a market. OATS, a Japanese company, agreed to supply the products to them in mid-2013. Nafees Ahmad are now focusing on field activities and advertising, categorizing their products with high and low-profit margins. Nafees Ahmad set up some new strategies and plans to boost their sales. Now Sungro have to improve their sales, which their sales managers can do, so Nafees Ahmad train their managers with Mr Sabahat Latif. In 2013, the closing percentage was 99%.

➤ *Expansion of the team to achieve targets*

The target set for 2014 was \$1.47 billion. The sales team increased from 65 to 87 people. Oats agreed to provide an "on-call" product, a granule-based product used to increase

maize production, and Nafees Ahmad covered all media outlets to promote it "ON CALL" Products were sold out with an "ON CALL" to increase sales. Market activities are similar in order to increase product sales. In mid-year, Japanese agriculture experts came from Japan, and met with farmers to resolve their issues, increasing the confidence level of the farmers and their employees to work more aggressively, which resulted in more sales and increased revenues. Now is the time to properly advertise and educate customers, so an agribusiness graduate with an MBA in marketing who understands all agriculture issues and techniques has been hire.

II. SUNGRO PRIVATE LIMITED

In 2015, the target was 2.5 million. Nafees Ahmad fully meet the target; increase the number of managers to monitor the workload appropriately. The OAT president came to Pakistan for a meeting in a hotel in Lahore with 1,000 farmers. That fantastic experience inspired their team to increase sales and re-engage former confident customers who no longer consider them. OATS' president was pleased to see the company clients' positive response and feedback on their ON CALL product. The company's owners successfully obtained new products from OATS's president and permission to produce local ON-CALL granules. The price was low, and sales were high. The company's total sales have now reached \$2.5 billion.

➤ *Objective:*

- To enhance the student's knowledge and help they start their businesses.
- To learn about different aspects of sales and marketing.
- To assists students in understanding the current market position, allowing them to solve real-world problems and offer solutions.

➤ *Case Study/Subject:*

Sales and marketing are the subjects on which the case study is mostly based on, and it discuss different strategies and plans to make a company profitable. How to advertise the company and its products to attract customers.

➤ *Target Audience:*

- Undergraduate student

➤ *Questions:*

Q1: What are a franchise and a franchise system?

A person's or company's right or permission to sell a company's goods or services in a specific location. In addition, a company awarded such a right or license-built a new pesticide franchise down the street.

Q2: What marketing strategies are they using?

The marketing department follows the above-the-line marketing (ATL) and below-the-line marketing (BTL) strategies. In ATL, marketing mass media channels used to target a broader range of customers in a shorter period. On the other hand, in BTL marketing, the company uses this strategy when they target a specific group of customers for their

product and then advertise on radio, television, print media, etc. They also create marketing materials for franchises to help them break into new markets.

Q3: What strategy are they using to increase their sales?

They decided to hire marketing help to guide people through the advertising process, and they held seminars and marketing activities. They target the focus customer (the farmer) and work on it. They begin by emphasizing their core customer and repeatedly emphasizing brands in every gathering to boost sales. The strategy increases customer follow-through, and they expect to reach 350 million by August. They have completed their first year with 480 million of their target.

They introduced their market-loving product with more effective advertisements. Their current focus is on customer segments. They increase the promotion of their product, and the company for this large gathering is suitable for them. In a short time, they can approach many customers with the help of their bold and potential customers. This gives farmers more confidence in attracting consumers to their products. OATS agreed with them to provide the products. They are now focusing on field activities and advertising, categorizing their products with high and low-profit margins. They set up some new strategies and plans to boost their sales. Now they have to improve their sales, which their sales managers can do, so they train their managers with Mr Sabah at Latif.

Q4: How did they boost their sales and marketing team?

Oats has agreed to provide an "on-call" product. A product made of granules that were used to increase maize production. They heavily publicize their new monopoly product and cover all media outlets to promote it "ON CALL." Products are now sold with an "ON" call to increase sales. Market activities are similar in order to increase product sales. In mid-year, Japanese agriculture experts came from Japan. They met with farmers to resolve their issues, increasing the confidence level of the farmers and their employees to work more aggressively, which resulted in more sales and increased revenues. Now is the time to properly advertise and educate customers, so an agribusiness graduate with an MBA in marketing who understands all agriculture issues and techniques, hired.

Q5. What strategy did they initially select, and how did they achieve success?

The sales team initially had only 45 people on four wheels. Then they set up a franchise system in their company for this, and they have to hire a one-franchise manager to control it and set up a meeting with the dealers to work with them. After that, they make a sales and marketing team run their operation correctly. Beyond all these, they must remove many other problems before adequately introducing themselves to the market. The first thing is to decide on the franchise selection—what dealer they have to work with; another decision is product selection—what kind of products they have to launch at the time of the company's launch and what strategy they have to adopt or plan to use to sell their product in the market. The central point was team development. How do you train them? How do they approach

farmers? What sales call do they put in front of them to attract them toward their products? Lastly, they have to plan the rules and regulations for their company.

Now the department of the company on which the whole company depends is the marketing department. The marketing department follows the above-the-line marketing (ATL) and below-the-line marketing (BTL) strategies. In ATL, marketing mass media channels used to target a broader range of customers in a shorter period. On the other hand, in BTL marketing, the company uses this strategy when they target a specific group of customers for their product and then advertise on radio, television, print media, etc. They create marketing materials for franchises to introduce them to new markets. Who are we? Then they set up the sales call pitch for their sales and marketing teams to interact with customers and introduce themselves. All the central points are written down in the literature, like the rules and regulations followed by the franchise. Why does any dealer become a franchise?

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology used in this case is the qualitative method (interview). Author himself meet with the GM of the company, and discussed the various aspects of the company that how it started. From the planning phase until now, we have discussed each point of their strategies, that how they succeeded.

Table 1 Teaching plan: In-person

Sr. No	Activity	Time
01	Every student should read it carefully	20 minutes
02	Brainstorming/ Discussion	25 minutes
03	Answers to each question	45minutes(9mins*5 questions)

Table 2 Online Format

Sr. No	Activity	Time
01	Every student should read it carefully	20 minutes
02	Brainstorming/ Discussion	25 minutes
03	Answers to each question	45minutes(9mins*5 questions)

Table 3 Hybrid/ dual mode

Sr. No	Activity	Time
01	Every student should read it carefully	20 minutes
02	Brainstorming/ Discussion	25 minutes
03	Answers to each question	45minutes(9mins*5 questions)

➤ *Teaching strategy*

The teaching strategy is straightforward and unique. We put some random questions in the full case study. As students read it at every phase, they face questions like Who are we? What rules and regulations were follow by the franchise?

Why does any dealer become a franchise? These are trigger questions to open the case discussion in class, and these little questions conclude the discussion so the audience understands the whole story of the case study.

➤ *Teaching experience*

The student's response was positive; they understood the students solved the whole scenario systematically because of the little questions in an entire case study at every phase in which they faced problems and that problems. They solved the queries on their own, and the results were so unique whole class enjoyed this case a lot. They feel like the owner of this company resolves the queries on its own

IV. CONCLUSION

This case were related to the agriculture company and how Mr Nafees started the company by making teams for sales, marketing, and other departments. The company's most essential and highlighted department is sales and marketing, which generates sales and produces revenue. They trained their sales team, set their sales call, introduced a franchise system, and selected products. Sungro started on January 5, 2012, with 45 people in the sales and marketing team who are on vehicles. In 2013, they revised the strategy of targeting the customer to increase their sales with the help of the sales and marketing departments. They focus on improving the sales and marketing departments through training from some popular Pakistani trainers to set up their sales calls and cover up their weak points. In 2014, they had an agreement with a Japanese company to give them a monopoly product, which they launched to capture the market with the help of the Japanese company, which boosted the sales teams. They spend more on advertising their product and company through all advertising channels. The visit by that Japanese company was a powerful strategy they used to gain the trust of their customers.

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